

SEADE

STRENGTHENING THE
EUROPE-AFRICA
DIGITAL ECOSYSTEM
THROUGH INCREASED
R&I COOPERATION

Deliverable 2.1

Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

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WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

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Document Control Sheet

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WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

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1 Executive Summary

Inset you will find a detailed account of the policies and strategies as well as the key initiatives in the Digital Research and Innovation space that support and enhance Digital cooperation between Europe and Africa. The results were an effort of desk research studies, interviews with a Human Centered Design approach and targeted surveys in 4 pilot regions in Africa (Ghana, Senegal, South Africa and Kenya). Key databases that were useful in the desk research included the European Commission online resources, per pilot region national databases on policies and strategies and suggested sources from the consortium partners. The interviews and surveys targeted researchers, STEM students, University professors and lecturers, government decision makers, policy makers, civil society and the full umbrella of technology players.

Overall, **over 100 policies and strategies** were collected that touched on both the EU-AU cooperation and each of the pilot regions digital research and innovation space. A total of **37 organizations** across the pilot regions participated in the interviews and **221 persons responded** to the survey. Regarding the initiatives contributing to the AU – EU cooperation which were fundamental in the definition of suitable tools and services that could enhance SEADE activities, over 300+ initiatives were found from impotent sources such as the **Global Gateway initiatives, AU-EU digital innovation agenda, the African Union initiatives** and from the policies and strategies collected initially.

The policies and strategies **provided gaps** affecting the cooperation between Africa and Europe in the digital R&I space **and possible recommendations** for reducing these gaps. **The gaps spanned** Limited infrastructure, Digital divides, Inadequate regulatory frameworks, Cybersecurity threats, automation's impact on jobs, data sovereignty and privacy, reliance on foreign technology, Capacity Building and Technical Assistance, Monitoring, Evaluation, and Enforcement, regulatory barriers, socio-cultural effects and Digital literacy and skills gap. **Some recommendations to solve these gaps included:** prioritizing investments, affordable access of digital technologies, clear guidelines to public-private partnerships, cybersecurity and trust initiatives, comprehensive data governance framework and curriculum integration.

The final section of the report provides the **key tools and services** extracted from the initiatives that will later influence activities in the succeeding work packages. The initiatives span different domains such as the green transition, digital, education and health sectors. The services are in various areas such as capacity building, funding and market. This report will serve as the foundation for the succeeding deliverable 2.2 in Work Package 2.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Table of Contents

1	Executive Summary	4
2	INTRODUCTION	6
2.1	Methodology	7
2.1.1	Collection and Analysis of the Digital and R&I Policies and Strategies	7
2.1.2	Collection and analysis of existing initiatives and tools	15
3	DIGITAL AND R&I POLICIES AND STRATEGIES ACROSS THE AU-EU AND THE SSA REGION .	16
3.1	Policies and Strategies across the AU-EU.....	17
3.1.1	Policies and strategies.....	17
3.1.2	Challenges and Recommendations	21
3.2	Policies and Strategies in Ghana	23
3.2.1	Policies and Strategies	23
3.2.2	Challenges and Recommendations	26
3.3	Policies and Strategies in Kenya.....	28
3.3.1	Policies and Strategies	28
3.3.2	Challenges and Recommendations	30
3.4	Policies and Strategies in the Senegal.....	32
3.4.1	Policies and Strategies	32
3.4.2	Challenges and Recommendations	34
3.5	Policies and Strategies in the South Africa.....	35
3.5.1	Policies and Strategies	35
3.5.2	Challenges and Recommendations	39
4	INITIATIVES	41
4.1	Tools and Services	44
5	CONCLUSION	45
6	ANNEXES.....	46
	List of Key Policies Per Region	46
	List of Key Strategies Per Region	48

2 INTRODUCTION

This report provides a **comprehensive summary of the digital and research and Innovation policies/strategies** that define and guide the digital transformation in **four selected pilot African countries: Ghana, Kenya, Senegal and South Africa** and enable cooperation and digital exchange between the African continent and the European Union. It further **highlights key initiatives and projects** from the Global Gateway/Team Europe and others that have or are currently making an impact in the digital development and growth in the respective pilot regions and the AU-EU. This exercise has the goal of learning the **state of the existing gaps in policy/strategy** from two perspectives: a lack of or a barrier in implementation and the provided recommendations in bridging these gaps. The initiatives and projects provide a rich knowledge base of some of the **successful digital tools and services** that have been developed and implemented in the respective regions. SEADE will then use this knowledge to guide the focus and implementation of its impact activities. A mapping of the result of this exercise is illustrated in figure 1 below.

Figure 1: Summarized mapping of R&I and digital policies/strategies and initiatives/tools across the AU-EU

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

2.1 Methodology

The study employed human-centred research approach as defined in Work Package 1. The mapping exercise involved two main tasks: collection and analysis of the Digital and R&I policies and strategies and collection and analysis of existing initiatives and tools. This was done in the first six months of the project with an additional three months for compilation, deliberation and finalization of this report. The first task was led by the Association of African Universities (AAU) and the second by WAZIUP e. V. (WAZI). A detailed process for each of the tasks in the sections that follow.

2.1.1 Collection and Analysis of the Digital and R&I Policies and Strategies

All the 4 pilot regions: Ghana, Kenya, Senegal and South Africa were involved in this exercise. Each region had the following tasks:

- To gather policy documents and strategies.
- To conduct literature reviews.
- To administer surveys to policymakers and local stakeholders.
- To conduct one-on-one interviews.

At the end of this exercise, each pilot region leader submitted the analysis report of their literature review in a completed Excel spreadsheet (available in the annex), and the transcripts of the one-on-one interviews conducted. Additionally, a survey was conducted across the broader sub-Saharan Africa region by AAU, accessible via the following link: <https://forms.gle/WK8oySgsPpgswU3y7> .

Desk Research process and results

The first level of the desk research process involved the collection of key data points from the policy and strategy documents found in literature. The documents included **existing reports, strategy documents, articles and position papers**. Each pilot region begun with the **main digital policies per region** and based on the priorities, sub-policies and strategies with their sub-strategies were defined. For example, for most countries **skill and innovation** is a priority defined by the main policy document. This is also linked to the focus of the SEADE project. This then works as a tracking channel for sub-policies for skill and innovation and strategies per region that align with it. The main policy document can have several priorities. In this case, a focus on a few of the priorities is defined and their sub-policies and strategies are searched for accordingly. The key data points extracted from the documents are shown in figure 2 below and included:

- The main objectives from the policies
- The target sector
- Implementation plan

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- Key outputs/outcomes
- Alignment with EU values
- The gaps identified
- Recommendations from the gaps

Document Information (metadata)	Objectives	Target Sector	Implementation Strategies/ Activities	Outputs/Outcomes and Impact	Alignment with EU Values	Gaps identified	Recommendations
National Information, Communications and Technology (ICT) Policy	1. Create the infrastructure conditions that enable the use of always-on, high speed, wireless, internet across the country. 2. Facilitate the creation of infrastructure and	1. Mobile First 2. Market 3. Skills and Innovation 4. Public Service Delivery	1. Mobile First - The Government will continue to invest in infrastructure for universal, always-on, high speed, wireless data connectivity for every citizen. The government will provide the network, storage and processing infrastructure, compute and	1. Mobile First - ensuring that every Kenyan has reasonable access by focusing on mobile and wireless infrastructure. 2. Market - It will enable a 24hr economy, enforce the use of the Mobile Public	Aligns with the EU value of Equality where every Kenyan is given access to mobile and wireless resources, market, skills and innovation and service.	1. Unequal investment and access to ICTs in un-served and under-served areas within Kenya 2. The under-utilisation of ICTs in the provision of government services and the	- creation of an enabling environment for all citizens and stakeholders

Figure 2: Extract of the excel sheet collection template with the main data extracted from the literature review process

This was done for the sub-Saharan region (SSA) as well as those that define the cooperation between the AU and the EU. Additionally, Trade and Industry insights were collected from the documents.

A summary of the total number of documents collected per category is shown in table 1 below.

Item	Number
Number of policies	54
Number of strategies	64
Trade and Industry related	18
Policies from SSA	33
Strategies from SSA	46
AU - EU related policies	21
AU - EU related strategies	16

Table 1: Total number of documents collected per category for all the regions

The per region collection exercise result is also shown in the table 2 below. This provides a contextualized summary of the documents that relate to various priorities per region.

Item	Kenya	Ghana	Senegal	South Africa
Number of policies	20	23	6	5
Number of strategies	20	15	21	8
Trade and Industry related	9	4	4	1
Policies from SSA	9	16	5	3
Strategies from SSA	11	8	21	6

Table 2: Total number of documents collected per category in each of the selected pilot regions

Interviews

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Additional to the literature reviews, one-on-one interviews were conducted in the respective pilot regions with experts in:

- **Policy;** from government ministries, parastatals and the private sector
- **Leads in the research and innovation space,** such as professors, lecturers, students, researchers, incubation leads, startup founders and freelance innovators.

The purpose of these interviews was to assess the alignment the information found in the literature review process with the regional context. It also provided a better picture of the digital and research and innovation space in each of the pilot region through **personalized views and experiences** from the interviewees. This was in-line with the **Human Centered Design (HCD) approach** which is the preferred methodological approach by the Global gateway and the SEADE project. A summary of the stakeholders interviewed are shown in the table 3 below. Their insights and opinions were also summarised in the form of a report from each of the pilot regions.

<i>Country</i>	<i>Organization</i>
<i>Ghana</i>	CSIR-INSTI (Institute for Scientific and Technological Information)
	CSIR-CRI (Crop Research Institute)
	University of Cape Coast
	Centre for Applied Research and Innovation in Supply Chain Africa, KNUST (CARISCA)
	Institute of ICT Professionals, Ghana (IIPGH)
	Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology, and Innovation (MESTI)
	Ghana Tertiary Education Commission (GTEC)
	CSIR-STEPRI (Science and Technology Policy Research Institute)
	Heritors Labs
<i>Senegal</i>	Incubateur ISM
	Interface SAS
	Soreetul
	LAfricaMobile
	Ambassade de France au Sénégal
	Expertise France

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

	Délégation générale à l'Entreprenariat Rapide des Femmes et des Jeunes (DER/FJ)
	École Supérieure Multinationale Des Télécommunications (ESMT)
	Dakar Institute of technology (DIT)
	AFI - L'Université de l'Entreprise (AFI L'UE)
	Polaris ASSO
	CTIC
	Sen-Startup
	PACE (Pan African Consortium of Experts)
	IRD (Institut de Recherche pour le développement)
Kenya	@iLabAfrica
	DeKUT Innovators Club
	Dedan Kimathi University of Technology (DeKUT)
	Strathmore University
	Ministry of ICT & e-governance, Nakuru
	KCA University
South Africa	MEST of Africa Head
	Startup bootcamp
	University of Cape Town
	University of Stellenbosch
	Western Cape Government: Department of the Premier
	Research ICT Africa
	The Western Cape Tourism, Trade and Investment Promotion Agency (Wesgro)

Table 3: List of stakeholders interviewed in each of the pilot regions

Key observations derived from the interviews include:

- **Strong Foundation of Existing Partnerships**

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Many stakeholders highlighted that there is already a strong foundation of collaboration between African Union (AU) and European Union (EU) member states in R&I. Several initiatives and projects, such as the Horizon 2020 and the Africa-Europe Innovation Partnership, have successfully fostered cooperation and shared knowledge between the two regions. This existing foundation can be leveraged to deepen and expand collaborative efforts, building on established relationships and successful past projects to tackle new and emerging challenges in the digital ecosystem.

- **Mutual Benefits and Shared Goals**

Stakeholders emphasized that AU-EU collaboration is mutually beneficial, with both regions sharing common goals such as sustainable development, technological advancement, and economic growth. European partners often bring advanced technological expertise and resources, while African partners provide unique insights, diverse perspectives, and opportunities for impactful application of innovations. The alignment of goals and mutual benefits is a strong driver for continued collaboration. Policies and programs that highlight these shared interests and promote win-win scenarios are likely to gain greater support and commitment from both sides.

- **Challenges in Policy Alignment and Implementation**

One of the significant challenges identified is the alignment and implementation of policies between the AU and EU. Differences in regulatory frameworks, bureaucratic processes, and priorities can create obstacles to seamless collaboration. Additionally, some stakeholders noted that while policies exist, their implementation often falls short, leading to gaps between policy intent and on-ground reality. Addressing these challenges requires harmonizing regulatory frameworks, simplifying bureaucratic processes, and ensuring that policies are not only well-designed but also effectively implemented. This calls for coordinated efforts and regular dialogue between policymakers from both regions.

- **Funding and Resource Allocation**

Stakeholders frequently pointed out issues related to funding and resource allocation. While there are numerous funding opportunities available, accessing these funds can be challenging due to complex application processes and stringent requirements. Furthermore, there is a need for more equitable distribution of resources to ensure that both large and small projects can benefit from collaborative efforts. Simplifying funding processes, providing capacity-building support to navigate funding applications, and ensuring a more equitable distribution

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

of resources are critical steps to enhance AU-EU collaboration. Developing joint funding mechanisms that are accessible and transparent can also help in addressing these challenges.

- **Capacity Building and Knowledge Transfer**

Capacity building and knowledge transfer were highlighted as key components of successful AU-EU collaboration. Stakeholders recognized the importance of training, mentorship, and skills development to empower researchers and innovators in both regions. However, there is still a need for more structured and sustained capacity-building programs that go beyond short-term workshops and seminars. Investing in long-term capacity-building initiatives that include mentorship programs, joint research projects, and institutional partnerships can significantly enhance the capabilities of researchers and innovators. Structured programs that facilitate continuous learning and knowledge exchange will contribute to building a more resilient and dynamic R&I ecosystem.

- **Impact of Cultural and Contextual Differences**

Cultural and contextual differences between the AU and EU regions can sometimes pose challenges to effective collaboration. Understanding and respecting these differences are crucial for successful partnerships. Stakeholders noted that efforts to bridge cultural gaps through intercultural training and inclusive communication strategies have been beneficial. Incorporating cultural sensitivity and contextual understanding into collaborative projects is essential. Intercultural training programs and inclusive communication strategies should be integral parts of AU-EU collaborations to foster mutual respect and understanding.

- **Opportunities for Digital Innovation and Market Expansion**

The rapid advancement of digital technologies presents significant opportunities for AU-EU collaboration. Stakeholders identified areas such as digital health, agriculture, fintech, and education as high-potential sectors for joint innovation. Additionally, expanding into new markets and leveraging each region's unique strengths can drive significant economic growth. Focusing on high-potential sectors and market expansion can yield substantial benefits for both regions. Joint initiatives that explore and capitalize on digital innovation opportunities should be prioritized, with a focus on creating scalable and sustainable solutions.

Surveys

A targeted survey was prepared and disseminated through customized email to the consortium's contact list and various innovation social media networks in both English and French. This survey was dichotomous, and it collected information on the opinions of various

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

thought leaders on the state of R&I in Africa. The key aspects considered were the challenges such as funding, regulatory frameworks, cooperation and collaboration, resources, role of education in government and on intellectual property rights. Demographic Information included roles, years of experience, organization types, and countries. This had the same target as the interviews.

221 respondents filled in the online survey. This was a good result as it exceeded the project KPI of 100. The respondents had 4 to 30+ years of experience. The survey is provided as the figure below as a sample.

Figure 3: Extract of the survey form disseminated to relevant stakeholders

The English and French survey data provided insights from stakeholders across various roles and countries. Here's a summary of the data and initial observations:

- **Policy Support:** Generally, respondents agree that current policies support R&I in the digital ecosystem, but there are notable differences in specific regions.
- **Funding Availability:** A significant number of respondents indicate insufficient funding, highlighting a critical barrier to digital innovation.
- **Collaboration Effectiveness:** Mixed responses, with some regions showing effective collaboration while others face challenges.
- **Regulatory Environment:** The regulatory framework is often seen as needing improvement to better support digital innovation.
- **Resources and Infrastructure:** Many respondents point out the lack of adequate resources and infrastructure, which hinders innovation efforts.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- **Role of Educational Institutions:** Educational institutions are seen as active but could do more to drive digital innovation.
- **Government Encouragement:** There is a perceived gap in government encouragement for adopting digital technologies in some regions.
- **Capacity Building:** There is a consensus on the need for better capacity building and skills development programs.
- **Intellectual Property Rights:** The intellectual property rights framework is viewed as inadequate by many respondents.
- **Private Sector Incentives:** More government incentives are needed to encourage private sector investment in digital innovation.

A graphical representation for two of the questions is as below:

Figure 4: The current policies in my country adequately support research and innovation in the digital ecosystem

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Figure 5: Collaboration between government agencies and local stakeholders is effective in promoting digital innovation response statistic

2.1.2 Collection and analysis of existing initiatives and tools

This data analysis for the initiatives was purely based on desk research. The global gateway/ Team Europe initiatives were the starting point for the research. These initiatives were first categorized as those applying to the whole of the SSA region and then those that apply to each of the countries of focus: Kenya, Senegal, Ghana, South Africa. An investigation of these initiatives provided a link to other related initiatives from different sources. These other sources included **FPI projects, the AU-EU innovation projects, PRIMA (Partnership for research and Innovation in the Mediterranean area), EURAXESS, BMZ (Foreign Ministry for Economic Development and Cooperation), GIZ (The Deutsche Gesellschaft für Internationale Zusammenarbeit (GIZ) GmbH or German Corporation for International Cooperation).**

An important classification of the initiatives was after the region was the domain or thematic area which fell under the Green Transition, Information and Technology, capacity of science, Digital, Education, Health and Transport. These initiatives served as a good resource to extract the previously implemented tools and services, their success level and potential of integration to SEADE services. A summary of collected initiatives is detailed in the later section of the report.

3 DIGITAL AND R&I POLICIES AND STRATEGIES ACROSS THE AU-EU AND THE SSA REGION

The Lome Convention of 1975, the [Cotonou Agreement of 2000](#) and the recent **Joint Africa EU strategy of 2007** define the long-standing relation between the AU and EU. The Lome convention defined the organization of African, Caribbean and Pacific States (OACPS) which strived to achieve sustainable development and progressive integration into the world economy of its member states. The Cotonou Agreement aimed at the reduction and eventual eradication of poverty while contributing to sustainable development and its revised edition (2010) included the fight against impunity and promotion of criminal justice through the International Criminal Court (ICC). This replaced the Lome convention and covers broader aspects with four main principles as:

- Equality of partners and ownership of development strategies
- Participation of external factors such as the civil society, the private sector, and the local governments.
- Signatories with mutual obligations enforced through dialogue
- Cooperation agreements vary according to each partner's level of development, needs, performance and long-term development strategies.

Ghana, Kenya, Senegal and South Africa are among the African countries that signed the Cotonou agreement and thus the priorities, policies and development agendas under this agreement apply to these countries which are the selected pilot regions for SEADE.

The [Joint Africa-EU Strategy \(JAES\)](#) outlines the basic principles and general objectives of the AU-EU partnership. It aims to reinforce political dialogue between Africa and Europe, expand AU-EU cooperation and promote a people-centred partnership. **Science, Technology and Innovation** plays a key role in all its highlighted 5 areas of cooperation which are:

- Peace and Security
- Democracy, good governance and Human Rights
- Human Development
- Sustainable and inclusive development and growth and continental integration
- Global and Emerging issues

In Human Development, **R&I is a pillar**, and it aims at promoting human capital development and **knowledge, skills-based societies and economies** by strengthening the link between education, training, science and innovation and better **managing mobility of people**. This strategy is defined further in **part 2.1.2** below along with the policies that guide its implementation.

The information provided in the sections that follow provides a summary of the analysis of the literature review, interviews and the survey used as the methodology of collecting data to

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

inform this report. The sections 2.2 to 2.5 that follow provide an alignment of policies and strategies with section 2.1 at the focus countries level for SEADE.

3.1 Policies and Strategies across the AU-EU

This section breaks down the joint Africa-EU strategy with a focus on the Human Development cooperation area to further define policies, other strategies and recommendations that affect its promotion areas: human capital development and knowledge, skill-based societies and economies. This will shed light on how **the cooperation will strengthen the link between education, training, science and innovation and to better manage the mobility of people.**

3.1.1 Policies and strategies

Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) is one of the most active areas of JAES. The [EU-Africa High Level Policy Dialogue \(HLPD\) on STI](#) formulates long-term research and innovation policy priorities to strengthen Africa-Europe cooperation. In July 2020, the thematic priorities for R&I based on the work of the HLPD were announced as:

- Innovation and Technology
- Green Transition
- Public Health
- Capacities for Science and Higher Education

The governing policy for the 4 priority areas is the [AU-EU Innovation Agenda](#), which proposes specific objectives with short, medium and long term actions for each of the HLPD priority areas. This was acknowledged in the final declaration of the summit to support cooperation between researchers and develop knowledge together as well as sharing knowledge and expertise. The AU-EU innovation agenda cites important policies and strategies as key motivations of enabling the AU -EU R&I cooperation as: **United Nations (UN) Agenda 2030, The AU Agenda 2063, the STI Strategy for Africa (STISTA 2024), the AUC Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa 2020-2030, Comprehensive strategic for Africa, the global approach to Research and Innovation and the Global Gateway.**

The AU-EU innovation agenda identifies five needs and gaps following a detailed analysis of previous and ongoing joint R&I activities. These five needs and gaps are:

- The innovation ecosystem
- Innovation Management
- Knowledge exchange, including technology transfer
- Access to finance
- Human Capacity Development

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Details of the analysis are provided in the AU-EU document. The agenda focuses on 3 objectives.

- Make it real- Translate innovative capacities and achievements of AU and EU researchers and innovators across sectors directly into tangible outputs.
- Generate Impact by Design – Foster and/or strengthen innovation ecosystems to enhance socio-economic impact on the ground through the exchange of knowledge, technology, competences and human resources.
- Strengthen people, communities and institutions – develop sustainable, long-lasting and mutually beneficial higher education, research and partnerships between AU and EU countries.
- Learn, Monitor and scale it up – scale up instruments that can take forward existing successful bilateral or multilateral programmes and projects between AU and EU partners.

Higher Education

The [Africa Summit Roadmap 2014-2017](#) provides an expanded view for the AU-EU plan for higher education. It discusses the dissemination of results of scientific and technical research, plans for mobility, use of transparency and recognition tools and strengthening the services delivery of Higher Education Institutions (HEI). It cites key programmes such as the [Erasmus+ programme](#) and [Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions](#) as key programmes that enhance the quality of learning for **African and European students, scholars, researchers and staff**. The [Nyerere mobility programme](#) allowed the mobility of **70 academic and administrative staff**. It mentions the importance of this as increasing the competitiveness and attractiveness of the institutions.

It further mentions the development of centres of excellence in Africa and the expansion of the **African Higher Education Harmonization** and the **Tuning Pilot initiative** which will:

- enhance the relevance and the quality of the curriculum,
- introduce **outcome-based teaching and learning**
- increase in the number of participating universities from 60 to 120

It also discusses the exchange to **foster education, vocational training and entrepreneurship among women and youth**.

Based on interests and need, further research can be done on the African Higher Education Harmonization policies and strategies, the Tuning Pilot initiative and the Quality assurance initiatives proposed in the document.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Mobility, Migration and Employment

The [Joint EU – Africa Declaration on Migration and Development](#) (MME) is the defining policy that reflects objectives of creating better jobs in Africa and better managing migration flows between the two continents. It aims to ensure sustainable development through better management of and cooperation on MME issues. It pushes for the implementation of relevant international agreements and declaratins such as the [Tripoli Declaration on Migration and Development](#), the [Ouagadougou Action Plan to Combat Trafficking in Human Beings especially women and children](#) and the [Ouagadougou Declaration and Plan of Action for Promotion of Employment and Poverty Alleviation \(Ouagadougou PoA\)](#).

With the concern that Africa is the least productive region in the world, the AU developed the [Productivity Agenda for Africa](#) with social dialogue guidelines. This is concerned with increasing the value, productivity and competitiveness of African Economies, improvement of productivity culture in Africa and mobilization of all relevant stakeholders to address productivity more actively.

The Ouagadougou PoA enacted two instruments to promote labour migration and Regional Economic Integration. These were the [programme on upgrading the informal economy](#) and the [Social Protection Plan for the Informal Economy and Rural Workers \(SPIREWORK\)](#). The two programmes still at the development level discuss the inclusion of the informal sector to the working environment as it contributes to 42 % of the Gross National income in Sub Saharan countries.

The Ouagadougou +10 policy areas have six priority areas:

- Political Leadership, Accountability and Good governance.
- Youth and Women Employment.
- Social Protection and Productivity for Sustainable and Inclusive Growth.
- Well-functioning and inclusive Labour Market Institutions.
- Labour Migration and Regional Economic Integration.
- Partnership and Resource Mobilization.

A look into Youth and Women employment and Labour Migration and Regional economic Integration can provide further policies, strategies and initiatives to enhance mobility between the AU and EU. The [International Organization of Migration](#) (IOM) website also provides additional resources on mobility between the AU and EU.

Trade and Industry

[Agenda 2063](#) emphasizes on trade as key in developing economies and ensuring economic growth and development. It cites Africa as being fundamentally a raw materials supplier in exchange for manufactured goods which renders the **continents share in global trade**

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

insignificant. The policy proposes key continental frameworks and flagship projects to add value to Africa’s commodities, reduce and remove barriers to intra-African trade and create a larger market for African goods and services.

The [African Continental Free Trade Area \(AfCFTA\)](#) is the flagship initiative of Agenda 2063 which works towards a continental geographic zone where goods and services move among member states of the AU with no restrictions. [Boosting Intra African Trade \(BIAT\)](#) aims to deepen African market integration and significantly increase the volume of trade that African countries undertake amongst themselves. The Action plan for Accelerated Industrial Development of Africa (AIDA) aims to mobilize both financial and nonfinancial resources and enhance Africa’s Industrial performance. The [commodities strategy](#) identifies, formulates and drives the implementation of policies and programmed that will drive African countries to add value, extract higher rents from their commodities and integrate into global value chains.

The [EU and AU are key partners](#) in Trade. Several Trade Agreements exist that boost sustainable development in Africa including 5 Economic Partnership Agreements (EPAs) applied with 14 countries and 4 Association Agreements (AAs) with countries in North Africa. 34 African countries benefit from the General Scheme of Preferences – Everything but Arms (GSP/EBA). EPAs are key in the EUs comprehensive strategy with Africa promoting sustainable development through enhanced trade relations and regional economic integration.

The [African Digital Compact](#) highlights the Africa Continental Free Trade Area from a Digital Trade perspective. It cites the protocol on Digital Trade as fundamental in AfCFTA that aims to promote the emergence of African-owned e-commerce platforms at National, Regional and Continental levels. It presents a roadmap of an Africa where digital trade barriers are minimized and technological opportunities maximized.

Other key resources to review include:

- [Science, Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa](#)
- African Union Digital Transformation Strategy (2020 – 2030)
- Draft Conceptual Framework for the Continental Artificial Intelligence Strategy
- Draft African Child Online Safety and Empowerment Policy
- African Union Data Policy Framework
- AU Interoperability Framework for Digital ID
- Strategy on Enabling Policy and Regulatory Environment for Africa’s Digital Single Market
- Malabo Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection
- Draft Guidelines for the Integration of Data Provision in Digital Trade protocols
- [European Data Strategy](#)

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- European Digital Single Market
- United Nations Process on Developing the Global Digital Compact
- African Union Agenda 2063
- The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA Digital Trade)
- Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa

3.1.2 Challenges and Recommendations

Africa's digital landscape and transformation journey is characterized by a unique set of challenges, including.

- **Limited infrastructure** - addressed through the **pillar 2 of the African Digital Compact**. Investment Priority: Accelerate investments in the development and modernization of digital infrastructure. This includes the expansion of broadband networks, the establishment of data centres, and the deployment of 5G technology to enhance connectivity and digital service delivery
- **Digital divides** – addressed through the **pillar 1 of the African Digital Compact**: Ensuring Affordable Access to Digital Technologies through ensuring Equitable and affordable access to digital technologies and services. Divides include but not limited to, gender, age, language, educational, technological, cultural, geographical, social, and economic divides.
- **Social inclusion** - The African Union strategy for gender equality and women empowerment provides a synergy in promoting digital inclusion and empowerment for women and girls in the digital sphere. It lists the following objectives as a starting point for addressing this gap:
 - Promote women and girls' access to ICT and STEM education
 - Ensure the participation of women in the digital economy and ICT-related careers
 - Address and eliminate gender-based digital divides
 - Enhance the safety and security of women and girls online

It provides the following initiatives to implement these objectives:

- Curriculum Integration designed to be inclusive and accessible, particularly among women, youth, and in rural areas.
- Teacher and Trainer Empowerment emphasizing pedagogical approaches suited to digital education.
- Online Learning Platforms and Resources that cater to a range of skills and competencies.
- Community Digital Hubs especially in underserved and rural areas, to provide access to digital learning resources and connectivity.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- **Inadequate regulatory frameworks** - addressed through the **pillar 2 of the African Digital Compact**. To develop and implement policy and regulatory frameworks that encourage investment in digital infrastructure. This involves the formulation of clear guidelines for **public-private partnerships (PPPs)** and incentives for private sector investments in infrastructure projects. Addressed in other pillars also.
- **Cybersecurity threats** - addressed through the **pillar 6 of the African Digital Compact: Enhancement of Cybersecurity and Data Protection**. Through Strategic initiatives such as: Cybersecurity and Trust, Legislative and Regulatory Frameworks, conforming to protection of Peace, Stability and Good Governance, Capacity Building and awareness, collaboration and partnerships, Innovation technology and development, Standards and best practices.
- automation's impact on jobs,
- data sovereignty and privacy - addressed through the **pillar 9 of the African Digital Compact: Safeguarding Digital Rights and Privacy** through Comprehensive Data Governance Framework and Data Protection Legislation, Privacy by Design and Default, Public Awareness and Education, Cross-Border Data Protection Cooperation,
- reliance on foreign technology, Capacity Building and Technical Assistance, Monitoring, Evaluation, and Enforcement.
- regulatory barriers,
- socio-cultural effects
- **Digital literacy and skills gap**- addressed through the **pillar 7 of the African Digital Compact: Enhancement of Digital Skills and Literacy** with the following strategic initiatives, Curriculum Integration, Teacher and Trainer Empowerment, Public-Private Partnerships for Digital Education, Online Learning Platforms and Resources Community Digital Hubs, Innovation in Digital Education, Monitoring and Evaluation.
- and deeply engaging community stakeholders.
- **Mobility challenges due to**
 - the large number of KPAs, Strategies and Recommendations.
 - the lack of financial resources at all levels.
 - the weakness of labour market institutions.
 - the persistent weak political will with concrete commitment.
 - the poor coordination between institutions concerned by the challenges of the labour market. Regarding the mentioned challenges, the Regional Economic Communities (RECs) should have played a central role in the implementation process of the Plan of Action, but they did not have the required human capacity to so do.

3.2 Policies and Strategies in Ghana

Ghana's commitment to fostering Research and Innovation (R&I) and digital transformation is evident through a comprehensive array of policies and strategies that span various sectors, including education, agriculture, industry, and technology. These frameworks are pivotal for creating an ecosystem that promotes scientific advancement, technological growth, and socio-economic development. Despite the absence of a dedicated R&I policy, the **national's broader Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) policy** integrates various aspects of research, including **education, human capacity building, and infrastructure development**. The Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology, and Innovation (MESTI) is central to shaping Ghana's R&I landscape, and the Ministry of Trade and Industry is responsible to the responsible for the trade and industry ecosystem, with the support of other government ministries and agencies, universities and research institutions, NGOs and international organizations, Start-ups and Innovation Hubs, and the private sectors and industry associations.

3.2.1 Policies and Strategies

The [National Science Technology and Innovation policy](#) (NSTI) is the main policy document currently under the process of adoption in Ghana that strongly emphasizes on innovation as key in the actions, policies and programmes applying to science and technology for development. Whilst it has undergone several challenges and iterations for development, the Ministry of Environment, Science, Technology, and Innovation (MESTI) established under the same mandate has been responsible for the various iterations in its development and its push for enactment. Supporting bodies and organizations include the Ghana Academy of Arts and Science (GAAS), the council for Scientific and Industrial Research (CSIR), Ghana Atomic Energy Commission (GAEC), Universities, and professional science and technology-based organizations. All policy formulation and implementation by these supporting organizations must align NSTI to provide proper oversight and advice on improvements or complete changes to be made in the Science and Technology environment.

The policy recommends various options to fund its activities. They include:

- Reforms on the funding lines supporting STI development
- Establishment of the National Science, technology and Innovation Fund
- Allocate a minimum of 1% of Ghana's GDP to support the science and Technology sector
- Attractive tax incentive scheme to benefit contributors to the STI fund and R&D activities

The [UNCTAD Report](#) provides a comprehensive analysis of STI policy for Ghana the ambitious plan for the to accelerate growth and increase productivity through R&I.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

The Government of Ghana has placed STI development high on its list of priorities. This is shown through the [Vision 2020](#), [The growth and poverty reduction strategy II \(GPRS II\)](#), and the [medium term development plan](#). The Vision 2020 provided the long-term vision of the country to become a middle-income economy by 2020. It cites science and Technology in both its current and mid-term objectives as part of the foundation for development for Ghana. The Growth and Poverty Reduction Strategy II identified the following 4 key priorities to enable the country overcome challenges of dependency on export earnings and low level of literacy and skills, especially among women and the rural population. These include:

- continued macroeconomic stability
- accelerated private sector-led growth
- **vigorous human resource development**
- good governance and civic responsibility

The human resource development which is a key priority in the **Joint Africa European Strategy (JAES)** highlights education as a key need and emphasizes on training, promotion of science and technology at all levels of education with particular attention to increased participation of girls and promotion of the adoption of the [National Youth Policy](#) and enactment of the Disability bill.

The National Youth Policy (2022 – 2032) under the Ministry of Youth and Sports and enacted under the African Youth Charter provides a comprehensive guide on addressing issues of the Youth for national development and their participation in global affairs. It cites the following key issues mainly affecting the youth in Ghana:

- economic and financial exclusion,
- adverse socio-cultural practices,
- a mismatch between knowledge acquired and industry requirements,
- inaccessibility of education and educational facilities,
- minimal skills development,
- low participation in governance,
- limited access to health services and
- weak development support services

The Policy touches on **youth unemployment and labour issues, youth migration and mobility, training and development, Education and Skills training, information and communications technology** amongst others which are closely linked to the priority areas of Human development in JAES.

As **36 percent of the Ghanaian population are youth**, emphasis is put on the providing quality education with hands-on experiences to its youth. Poor infrastructure, inadequate teaching equipment and learning aids, large class sizes with insufficient number of teachers, poor

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

motivation of teachers and inadequate supervision are cited as some of the hindering factors to provision of quality education. There are also few vocational and technical training programs. This is adverse as deviates from the global development plan of science, technology, engineering and Mathematics (STEM) which is key for industry needs.

Alongside the EU delegation, there are 9 EU member states that have a resident Ambassador in Ghana. These include Czech Republic, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, Italy, Malta, Netherlands and Spain. Ghana has a strong political relation with EU shown by their common priorities and the **EU-Ghana Partnership dialogue**. The launch of the EU-Ghana joint programming for [2021 to 2027: The future of EU-Ghana relations](#), will see the EU provide EUR 203 million for the period 2021 – 2024 in the following priority areas defined by the with its Team Europe partners and the Government of Ghana:

- Green Growth and Jobs (EUR 71 million)
- Smart and Sustainable Cities (EUR 71 million)
- Good Governance and Security (EUR 47 million)
- Support Measures (EUR 14 million)

Trade and Industry

Ghana is a member of the African Union as well as of other major international bodies. It is a longstanding member of the **World Trade Organization (WTO)**, a founding country of the regional **Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS)** and an early supporter of the **African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA)**, signed in 2018. The Secretariat of the AfCFTA is based in Ghana's capital, Accra.

Since 2016, Ghana is implementing an **Economic Partnership Agreement (EPA)** with the EU. The EU-Ghana EPA is a trade and development agreement under which Ghanaian exporters benefit from **duty-free and quota-free access** to the EU market. Equally, under the EPA, Ghana has agreed to open gradually (from 2021 till 2029) its market to around 80% of EU products, which will increase the country's competitiveness in the regional markets. Products that are sensitive in Ghana are excluded from liberalisation. Additionally, the EU is providing Ghana with **development cooperation and financial adjustment** support to help with the implementation of the iEPA. In addition, the EU is providing technical assistance to the Ministry of Trade and Investment for managing all obligations from the Agreement.

[The EU continues](#) to be one of the most important trade partners for Ghana. Value of exports/imports with the EU In 2022, the EU was Ghana's largest source of imports, accounting for 17.4% of Ghana's imports, ahead of China at 16.8 % and the USA at 11.5 % and the fourth-largest export destination, accounting for 11.3% of Ghana's export (behind China (23.3%), Switzerland (18.7%) and South Africa (15.7%)). Overall, the EU is accounting for

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

around 13.9% of Ghana’s total external trade in 2022, being the second most important partner after China (20.5%).

Ghana has both the [Ghana Industrial Policy](#) and the **Ghana Trade Policy, 2018** that details **programmes and projects** to be implemented to provide new direction to the public and private sector and to encourage growth and development of the Ghana’s industrial sector.

Other Key Resources

- United Nations World Programme of Action for Youth (2010)
- Commonwealth Plan of Action for Youth Empowerment (PAYE) 2006 - 2015
- AU Agenda 2063
- African Plan of Action for Youth Empowerment (APAYE)
- African Youth Charter (Article 12)
- Coordinated Programme of Economic and Social Development Policies (2017 -2024)
- National Medium Term Development Policy Framework (2022 - 2025)
- National Development Planning Commission (NDPC) – on participation of youth, girls and women, persons with disability and other vulnerable groups
- Youth in Agriculture
- Youth in ICT
- Youth Entrepreneurship and Innovation Programme
- National Builders Corps
- National Services Scheme
- Cybersecurity Act 2020, Act 1038
- Ghana Industrial Policy
- National Policy on Public private partnerships, 2011
- Ghana National Urban Policy, 2012
- Ghana National Climate Change Policy, 2013
- National Local Economic Development policy, 2013
- National Employment policy, 2015
- National Labour Migration Policy, 2020
- Ghana Trade Policy, 2018
- National Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises and Entrepreneurship Policy
- National Rural Development Policy, 2019
- [National AfCFTA Policy Framework and Action Plan \(for Boosting Ghana’s Trade with Africa\)](#)

3.2.2 Challenges and Recommendations

Key Challenges include:

- Inadequate scientific expertise in the country.
- Lack of effective advocacy for STI at the highest political and policy levels.
- Low science and technology culture among the populace.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- Weak structures for the management of STI.
- Ineffective coordination of the STI system
- Inadequate budget and resource allocation to STI.
- Weak linkage between policy formulation and national development planning.
- Weak mechanisms for implementation, evaluation and review of STI projects and initiatives.
- Weak linkages between various agencies and organizations in STI.
- Weak linkage between industry and the R&D system.
- Over reliance on the use of foreign expertise to the neglect of the use and development of local expertise.
- Inadequate science teaching and learning in our pre-tertiary education system.
- Poor remuneration and conditions of service for science and technology personnel of research institutions.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

3.3 Policies and Strategies in Kenya

The main document governing the **Digital and Research and Innovation policies** in Kenya is the [National Information, Communications and Technology \(ICT\) Policy document](#). This document was published in November 2019 and is in line with the following legal and regulatory frameworks; the [Kenya Information and Communications Act of 2011](#), the media council act of 2013 and the 2010 constitution of Kenya. It provides a comprehensive plan of the country's ambition on **infrastructure development**, leveraging of the **regional and international cooperation**, **skills development** and **digitization of government services**. This is with the purpose of keeping the country up to date with the global emerging trends in ICT such as **'The Internet of Things'**, **'Machine Learning'** and **'Big Data Management'** which increases the capacity of dignified jobs for its citizens.

The ICT policy proposes 4 focus areas to achieve this ambition:

- Mobile first – which ensures that every Kenyan has a reasonable access to internet connection and an internet enabled mobile phone
- **Market** – ensures Kenya's contribution to the global market through enabling of youth with access to digital jobs
- **Skills and Innovation** – re-assessment of the Research and Innovation priorities every two years
- Public Service Delivery – all government services to be provided online.

The sections that follow define this policy in detail and provide other relating policies and strategies for Digital R&I in Kenya. An aspect of Trade and Industry as well as EU-Kenya Cooperation is also covered in the text.

3.3.1 Policies and Strategies

The [National Digital Master Plan 2022 – 2032](#) derives from the ICT policy. It aims to provide a holistic and coordinated approach to ensure alignment and optimization of ICTs resources with changing needs. It streamlines ICT projects across government, ensures interoperability of systems by eliminating technology silos, share and reuse viable ICTs assets, guarantee privacy and data protection and provides Cyber Security Assurance. **It has also provided an elaborate 10-year government plan which guides ICT investors.**

The framework classified ICT components into **four pillars and foundational themes**. The pillars are:

- digital infrastructure,
- digital services and data management,
- digital skills

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- digital enterprises innovation and businesses.

The foundations are crossing cutting issues which among them are:

- emerging technologies,
- Cyber Security management,
- Policies and legislations
- Research and Development.

In recognition of the growth in the ICT sector as well as the rights to privacy guaranteed under article 31 of the constitution of Kenya, the Government recognized the need to have a framework in place that will regulate the **processing of personal information**. Subsequently, in April 2019, the executive assented to the **Privacy and Data Protection policy 2019**, which was followed by the enactment of the **Data Protection Act 2019**. In November 2020, Kenya's first Data Commissioner was appointed to spearhead the establishment and operationalization of the office of the Data Protection commissioner. In operationalizing the office, three sets of data protection regulations have been enacted. The regulations speak to the **rights of the data subjects** and **obligations of data controllers** as well as **data localization requirements**. Secondly, the requirement for registration and lastly as complaints and dispute resolution mechanism in relation to the processing of personal information.

East Africa Regional Trade and Development facilitation are among the initiatives currently under implementation by the Kenya Government.

The European Union is a significant trading partner to Kenya, representing Kenya's biggest export market with 21.1% of Kenya's total exports to the world. Kenya is the commercial hub for the EAC region due to its favourable location, skilled labour force and vibrant business community. **European companies** lead the way in investing in Kenya, generating jobs and tax revenue. The upcoming implementation of the **Economic Partnership Agreement** underscores the significance of the European Union trade relations with Kenya.

The [Trade Helpdesk](#) (previously known as the Export helpdesk) is an online service to facilitate market access for developing countries to the European Union. This is a free and user-friendly online service for exporters, importers, trade associations and governments.

Joint Cooperation Strategy 2018-2022 under which €4.5 billion in combined development aid will support the priorities and objectives of the national government, focused on the **Big Four agenda** (manufacturing, food security, universal health coverage and affordable housing). Based on Kenya's development strategy, the following sectors of concentration have been identified as priorities for European Union funding:

- Accountability and Governance.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- Sustainable infrastructure.
- Employment creation.
- Resilience building.

Other resources

- [Kenya Digital Economy Blueprint](#)
- Kenya National ICT Master Plan 2014 -2017
- Information Act No. 31 of 2016
- Computer Misuse and Cyber Crime Act 2018
- Data Protection Act No. 24 of 2019
- KENET
- Konza Technopolis Development Authority (KoTDA) Bill
- Annual Youth Mentorship programme
- Privacy and Data Protection policy 2019
- African Union Digital Transformation Strategy (2020-2030)
- Smart Africa Alliance Blueprint for the Digital Government
- Un Global Digital Government Models
- E-government strategy 2004
- The Master plan 2013
- Resource Mobilization Strategy
- Buffer Zone development control strategy
- Government paperless office strategy
- Artificial Intelligence strategy for Kenya
- Business continuity strategy
- Government digitization strategy
- Strategy to enhance security intelligence and surveillance of the country - proposed
- County automation strategy - proposed
- County e-waste policy – proposed
- ICT Product development strategy - proposed
- policies and legislations for IP protection for ICT products and services - proposed
- Capacity Building Strategy – proposed
- Innovation Strategy of the federal government in relation to the High-tech-Strategy Germany
- E-commerce strategy – proposed
- Manufacturing and Assembly Strategy – proposed
- **And many more** – refer to the Digital Master Plan
- [Internet of Things policy \(Europe\)](#)
- [Automotive and Transportation, Energy and Environment and healthcare policies](#)

3.3.2 Challenges and Recommendations

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Challenges

1. Framework - There was a lack of implementation framework and though ICTA later took charge in monitoring and coordinating the plan it came late since it was also being established.
2. Resources - Inadequate resources to implement the Master Plan.
3. Coordination - There was inadequate coordination to align Government entities to the Master plan.
4. ICTA Establishment - Delay in establishment and operationalization of ICT Authority. The ICT Authority was to play a critical role in coordination and implementation of the master plan and its delay in establishing the entity had THE KENYA NATIONAL DIGITAL MASTER PLAN 2022-2032 a negative significant impact on the success of implementation of the master plan.
5. Limited technical staff – The agencies tasked to implement the master plan had a limited number of technical staff.

Recommendations

1. Resource Mobilization- A more realistic resource mobilization strategy needs to be incorporated in the Master Plan to address the issues of finances, time, systems/tools and human capital. The country needs to have a policy on resource mobilization for the master plan.
2. Stakeholder Engagement and Communication: A stakeholder engagement plan and an elaborate communication plan need to be incorporated in the plan for citizen 'buy-in' and support for successful implementation.
3. Collaboration between Government Agencies – There is a need to have a collaborative approach during the implementation of the initiatives to ensure sustainability and ownership.

3.4 Policies and Strategies in Senegal

Implementation of STI policies in Senegal is done at the level of the [Ministère de l'Enseignement Supérieur, de la Recherche et de l'Innovation](#) (MESRI) (Ministry of Higher Education, Research and Innovation), and other ministries (e.g. Ministry of Industry, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Health), Universities and Research Institutes. MESRI is the main governing body for [science and technology \(S&T\) policy](#). In addition, MESRI defines the national priorities for S&T research and funds research through various funding instruments. Furthermore, it coordinates S&T activities and works in close collaboration with the technical ministries on which the research institutes depend.

3.4.1 Policies and Strategies

Senegal has actively participated in the development and adoption of the [STI policy of the Economic Community of West African States \(ECOPOST\)](#) and the [ECOWAS Research Policy \(ECORP\)](#). Senegal is also participating in the [African Initiative for STI Indicators \(ASTII\)](#). ECOPOST proposes creating a **solidarity fund** to help countries fund investment in key institutions, improve education and training **and attract foreign direct investment**. It advocates for development of science culture in all sectors of the society, dissemination of research results, commercialization of research results, technology transfer, intellectual property protection, **stronger university industry ties** and enhancement of traditional knowledge. ECOPOST discusses interesting topics such as:

- Adapt university curriculum to local industry needs
- Develop small research and training units in key industrial fields
- Establish science and technology parks and business incubators
- Help companies specializing in electronics to set up business in their country in areas such as remote sensing, environmental monitoring etc.
- Develop a national capacity to manufacture computer hardware and design software

[ECOWAS 2012 Annual Report](#), highlights ECORP under the **Human Development** results for the West African States. The goal of ASTII is to contribute towards better quality of STI policies at National, regional and continental levels. It lists key programs, initiatives and workshops that have led to the proper structuring of R&I in the West African Countries. Key events included: **Mapping Research and Innovation initiative institutions in COMESA region** and **Expert Group Meeting to Review the Draft African Innovation Outlook Report 2013** (AIO-2013) Human Sciences Research Council (HSRC).

The [Joint Strategy of the European Union and Senegal](#) aims to support Senegal's emergence, strengthen the country's stability and support its efforts to economic and social recovery following the COVID 19 crisis. It highlights the following 3 priorities:

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- Green and inclusive growth for job creation
- The development of human capital
- Good governance

Human Capital development emphasizes on Quality of Education, higher education and research, training and professional integration. It prioritizes on the strengthening of the employability of young Senegalese to ensure their professional integration, as employees or entrepreneurs, job creation by improving employability and professional integration by strengthening the vocational training offer. It emphasizes on providing the opportunities for young people, in line with the demand of the labor market, and the most promising sectors, such as the **digital sector**.

Senegal's economic and trade relations with the EU is pursued by supporting the strengthening of transport infrastructures of regional interest and the improvement of the competitiveness of the national economy. Team Europe (mainly France, Netherlands and Belgium) is Senegal's leading trading partner with 32% of imports and 12% exports. Senegal plans to apply for the **"Everything But Arms" system – TSA** which is the most favorable of the European Generalized System of Preferences (GSP+).

Other resources

- UNESCO Science Report
- UNESCO Institute of Statistics
- [West African Economic and Monetary Union](#)
- New Partnership for Africa's Development (NEPAD)
- African Innovation Outlook (AIO) Report 2010, 2014
- National Innovation System (NIS)
- An African exhibition of Research and Innovation in Senegal (SARIS)
- Agence Nationale de la Recherche Scientifique Appliquée (ANRSA)
- Fonds de Publication scientifique et technique (FPST),
- Fonds National de Recherche Agricole et Agro-alimentaire (FNRAA)
- Fonds de Promotion de l'Industrie Cinématographique et Audiovisuelle (FOPICA)
- Programme de réformes prioritaires in Senegal "(PRP)
- Plan de Développement de l'Enseignement Supérieur et de la Recherche "(PDESR)
- Plan Sénégal Emergent Strategy (PSE)
- Documents de Stratégie de Réduction de la Pauvreté (DSRP)
- Stratégie Nationale de Développement Economique et Social (SNDES)
- Plan d'Actions Prioritaires (PAP 1)
- Creation and promotion of startups in Senegal (Startup Act)

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- creation of the Senegalese Agency for Industrial Property and Technological Innovation (ASPIT)
- the law on the protection of personal data in Senegal
- [National Data Strategy Senegal](#)
- [Digital Senegal 2025 Strategy](#)

3.4.2 Challenges and Recommendations

From the National [Data Strategy Senegal](#) and the [Digital Senegal 2025 Strategy](#).

National Data Strategy of Senegal

Challenges:

Access to Quality and Reliable Data: Initiatives for data collection and usage often face challenges related to the quality, reliability, and access to up-to-date data.

Digital Inclusion: Disparities remain in terms of access to and quality of internet connectivity, especially in rural areas, which limits the adoption of new technologies.

Interoperability and Regulatory Framework: There is a need to develop a robust interoperability framework and update regulations to keep pace with the rapid technological advancements, especially in artificial intelligence.

Capacity Building: A persistent need exists to raise awareness and strengthen the capacities of stakeholders on the importance of data and emerging technologies

Recommendations:

Implementation of High-Performance Infrastructure: Improve digital infrastructures such as data centers and supercomputers to support data exploitation.

Development of an Interoperability Framework: Establish national standards and platforms to facilitate the exchange and use of data among different stakeholders.

Training and Awareness: Strengthen the capacities of stakeholders at all levels through dedicated programs for the use and management of big data.

Creating Synergies for Action: Encourage dialogue and cooperation among national, local, and community structures for better data production and usage

Digital Senegal 2025 Strategy

Challenges:

Digital Sovereignty and Cybersecurity: Strengthen national cybersecurity to protect the Senegalese cyberspace with legal, organizational, and operational measures.

Coordination of Interventions: Lack of effective coordination in cybersecurity interventions, requiring a dedicated agency and better integration of different digital security entities.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

Adapting Skills to New Digital Jobs: Need for more training in emerging technological fields like Big Data and Artificial Intelligence to prepare the youth for future jobs.

Recommendations:

Cybersecurity: Create a national agency dedicated to cybersecurity to coordinate efforts to protect data and digital infrastructures.

Training and Digital Innovation: Introduce digital skills in school curricula starting from primary education and develop specialized tracks in advanced technologies to support innovation.

Public-Private Partnerships: Develop collaborations with the private sector to create FabLabs and other innovation structures in regional capitals, thus supporting the country's digital entrepreneurial ecosystem.

Strengthening Digital Infrastructures: Continue investing in telecommunications infrastructures, including fiber optics and submarine cables, to enhance national and international connectivity.

3.5 Policies and Strategies in South Africa

The [1996 White Paper on Science and Technology](#), introduced the concept of the national system of innovation (NSI), a set of interacting organisations and policies through which South Africa creates, acquires, diffuses and puts into practice new knowledge to help achieve individual and collective goals. This defines the mandate of the **Department of Science and Innovation (DSI)** which is the governing body in South Africa that boosts socio-economic development through Research and Innovation. The department notes the following priorities to enable it strengthen South Africa's Research and Innovation ecosystem.

- Implementation of the National Space Strategy
- **Developing Human Capital**
- **Advancing innovation to improve South Africa's competitiveness in the global market**

Human Capital and Innovation as a priority is achieved through sub-policies highlighted in the sections that follow. The relationship between EU and South Africa for better cooperation is also detailed in the section that follows.

3.5.1 Policies and Strategies

A review of the **1996 White Paper on Science and Technology** led to a [new White paper](#) on STI and approved in March 2019. This was a result of a review process by the National Advisory Council on Innovation (NACI) on several initiatives such as the **2002 National Research and Development Strategy, The Ten-Year Innovation Plan (2008 – 2018), an analysis of the NCI performance, the first phase of an STI institutional review and a national STI foresight**

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

exercise looking towards 2030. This new white paper is aligned and shaped by the **National Development Plan (NDP)**. The NDP identifies science, technology, and innovation as critical for the creation of a competitive and sustainable economy and for addressing societal challenges such as education and health.

The [Decadal plan](#) 2022 – 2032 which is the implementation steps of the new White Paper highlights the following priorities for the R&I landscape in South Africa;

- Climate change including environmental sustainability
- The future of education skill and work
- The future of society

Section 3.3 explicitly discusses digital and circular economy as the new sources of the national growth strategy. It highlights key areas such as the **Internet of Things**, Artificial Intelligence, Blockchain technology as technologies of the future that opportunities as well as threats for the socio-economic systems. It further insists that regulation of these technologies is necessary on areas of security, privacy, equity and integrity. The Decadal plan seeks to respond to the imperatives of the **draft Digital Economy Masterplan** and recognizes that the development of the digital economy is essential to for any country's growth strategy.

The **National Intellectual Property Management Office (NIPMO)**, the **offices of technology transfer (OTTs)** and the **Technology Innovation Agency (TIA)** must ensure that, where appropriate, publicly funded R&D outputs result in products, processes or services for commercialisation or other positive impact on the lives of South Africans. **The Intellectual Property Rights from Publicly Financed Research and Development Act (IPR Act), 2008**, mandates the creation of OTTs at all institutions (26 HEIs and 11 science councils). The OTTs must receive disclosures of new intellectual property (IP) creations from researchers, analyse them for commercial potential and engage with TIA (and other funding agencies) for further development and exploitation. Among other things, the OTTs must seek IP protection where appropriate, conclude IP transactions (e.g. licences), establish start-up companies, receive revenue and share benefits with the IP creators.

To Stimulate STI and trade synergies, The UN General Assembly¹, in its 2019 resolution on STI for achieving the SDGs, noted the importance of a country's innovation index for measuring economic performance. In 2019, SA's technology balance of payments, a registry of commercial transactions related to technology and know-how transfers, totalled US\$1,7 billion, one of the lowest among the world's emerging economies. SA's science diplomacy will need to move from science-related initiatives to specific innovation and commercialisation initiatives. In this instance, the objective would be to draw on science diplomacy as an enabler to:

- improve opportunities for technology diffusion to benefit small firms.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- promote the commercialisation in foreign markets of IP filed in SA by technology start-ups and SMMEs that have been supported in kind or financially by the DSI.
- promote the commercialisation of publicly funded IP beyond SA's borders.
- make innovation and economic diplomacy the conduits for driving industrialisation and economic competitiveness.

South Africa is the EU's biggest partner in research and Innovation in Africa, and it is the first among African countries in participating to Horizon Europe. South Africa is an active member of the meetings of the Bureau of the [AU-EU High-Level Policy Dialogue on STI](#), and played an important role in the development of the [AU-EU Innovation Agenda](#), hosting in Cape Town the first ever [AU-EU Innovation Festival](#) in June 2023.

The EU and South Africa have enjoyed over 25 years of fruitful and successful cooperation in science, technology and innovation, with a bilateral [Science and Technology Cooperation Agreement](#) in force since November 1997. Bilateral scientific collaboration is monitored and facilitated by the Joint Science and Technology Cooperation Committee (JSTCC) established under the Agreement on Science and Technology, which is embedded into the joint overall [EU-South Africa Strategic Partnership](#). The Joint Science and Technology Cooperation Committee (JSTCC) monitors and facilitates cooperation between South Africa and the EU. [The last JSTCC meeting took place on 12 April 2019](#), and the next one is foreseen to take place in November 2024 in Cape Town. Areas of cooperation include;

- Health: [European and Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership \(EDTCP\)](#)
- Green Transition: [Group on Earth Observations \(GEO\)](#); [Climate Change and Sustainable Energy \(CCSE\)](#) Partnership; [Food, Nutrition Security and Sustainable Agriculture \(FNSSA\)](#) Partnership
- Healthy oceans and Seas: [All Atlantic Ocean R&I Alliance \(AAORIA\)](#)
- Innovation and Technology: [Square Kilometre Array \(SKA\)](#); [European South African Science and Technology Advancement Programme \(ESASTAP\)](#); [ENRICH in Africa Center](#); [EUREKA](#)

Key documents for Trade and Industry South Africa

- [Importing into the EU](#) from South Africa
 - o [EU trade defence measures on imports](#) from South Africa
- [Exporting from the EU](#) to South Africa
 - o [Trade defence measures in force in South Africa](#)
- Trade relations are part of [the EU's overall political and economic relations with South Africa](#)
- South Africa is a [member of the World Trade Organization](#)

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- [Sustainable impact assessment of the EU-African Caribbean Pacific Trade Relations of the Economic Partnership Agreements](#)

Other documents

- The NRDS Science Missions
- The NRDS technology missions and TYIP grand Challenges
- The National Advisory Council on Innovation (NACI) STI Foresight
- Draft Digital Economy Masterplan
- South African National Research Network
- Tertiary Education and Research Network
- National Industrial Participation program
- Trade and Industrial Policy
- Innovation Policy 3.0
- 2013 Youth Employment Accord
- The 2020-2030 National Youth Policy
- 2009 African Youth Charter
- 2005 Commonwealth Youth Charter
- Science Diplomacy Strategy
- STI Gender Strategy
- National Digital and Future Skills Strategy
- National Skills Development Strategy (NSDS) III
- National Big Data Strategy
- Science Technology and Innovation Strategy for Africa
- White Paper on e-Education: Transforming Learning and Teaching through Information and Communications Technologies (ICTs), 2004
- National Development Plan – Executive Summary, 2011 and full document
- National Skills Accord, 2011
- South Africa Connect: South African Broadband Policy, 2013
- White Paper for Post-School Education and Training, 2013
- National Integrated ICT Policy White Paper, 2016
- The Third National Skills Development Strategy, 2016
- South Africa's National e-Strategy, 2017
- National e-Government Strategy and Roadmap, 2017
- Integrated Justice System (IJS) Digital Transformation Strategy, 2017
- Professional Development Framework for Digital Learning, 2017
- DTPS Annual Performance Plan, 2017-2018
- IJS digital transformation strategy, 2017
- GITOC digital government strategy, 2018
- Artificial Intelligence Strategy and Ethics Framework
- Data Strategy to support NACI M&E Framework
- Protection of Information Act No. 84 of 1982

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

- Minimum Information Security Standards (MISS), 1996
- National Archives and Records Service of South Africa Act, Act No. 43 of 1996 (NARSSA)
- Promotion of Access to Information Act, Act No. 2 of 2000 (PAIA)
- Electronic Communications Act, Act No. 36 of 2005
- Electronic Communications and Transactions Act No. 25 of 2002 (ECTA)
- Spatial Data Infrastructure Act, Act No. 54 of 2003 (SDIA)
- National Cybersecurity Policy Framework, 2012
- Protection of Personal Information Act, Act No. 4 of 2013 (POPIA)
- Public Administration Management Act, Act No. 11 of 2014 (PAMA)
- National Integrated ICT Policy White Paper, 2016
- National e-Strategy, 2017
- Cybercrimes Act, 2020 (Act 19 of 2020) (CCA)
- The Regulation of Interception of Communications and Provision of Communication Related Information Act 70 of 2002 (RICA)
- DPSA Determination and Directive on the Usage of Cloud Computing Services in the Public Service
- [National Digital and Future Skills Strategy](#)

3.5.2 Challenges and Recommendations

The South African government faces challenges due to:

- **slow technology adoption** - leading to disjointed data collection, storage, and processing. Considering data as a key enabler for digital transformation and the digital economy, it is crucial to ensure equitable access to data to foster digital and economic inclusion. In a society marked by significant inequalities
- **The lack of common data governance mechanisms** hampers data integration, sharing, and system interoperability. This siloed approach results in lost opportunities for evidence-based policymaking, integrated planning, and making nonsensitive data available for innovation and the development of digital goods and services to support employment and reduce poverty.
- **Digital Inclusion** - the government must continually seek mechanisms to foster economic inclusion and bridge the gap between the rich and poor. Digital inclusion through affordable connectivity, data, and digital technology access is vital for achieving these goals, especially for small, medium, and micro enterprises (SMMEs) and startups, which have the potential to create jobs and contribute to economic growth. Digital inclusion should also focus on the indigent, the youth, women and people with disability to enable them, not only to be able to access government

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

services, but to also have access to data and internet connectivity to enable them to innovate and develop digitally tradable goods and services necessary to ensure their economic inclusion.

- **The absence of a regulatory environment** might deter increased investment in digital technologies as investors largely seek regulatory certainty to ensure adequate protection of their investments.
- **Energy Supply challenges** - Connectivity and utilisation of technologies should be supported by a reliable energy supply. South Africa has over time experienced energy supply challenges which has had a negative impact on government and industrial initiatives to grow the economy and foster economic inclusion. The functionality of most of the digital infrastructure relies significantly on reliable energy supply. Data centres also rely significantly on cooling systems that require vast volumes of water. In addition to energy supply challenges, issues of sustainability are beginning to take centre stage.
- **Cybersecurity** - In a global and digitally connected world driven by free data inflows and outflows, there is already a realisation that some countries establishing regulatory mechanisms to protect certain types of data regarded as critical for their security and sovereignty. In addition, there is also a recognition that data-sharing across different jurisdictions can also be beneficial to country economies. Collaborative economic developmental initiatives like the African Continental Free Trade Area, (ACFTA), the African Single Digital market and digital identity will rely significantly on data-sharing within different jurisdictions.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

4 INITIATIVES

This section lists the digital initiatives under the Global Gateway, ICT58 projects, FPI projects, projects under the AU and priority projects according to the Digital development plan for each of the selected countries. It classifies them according to their region of application, category (Digital, Green Transition, Transport, Education, and Health). These are provided in the table below:

Region	Theme	Initiative
AU - EU	Digital	African-European Digital Innovation Bridge Network (AEDIB NET)
		Africa-Europe Digital Regulators Partnership in Sub-Saharan Africa
		AfricaConnect4 in Sub-Saharan Africa
		EU-AU Data Flagship
		Team Europe Initiative on Data Governance in Africa
		D4D
		The first Trans-continental Networking Academy for African and European Digital Innovation Hubs (AfriConEU)
		African European Maker Innovation Ecosystem (mAke)
		Paving the Foundation for Disruptive Technologies in Tomorrow's Digital Innovation Hubs (HUBiquitous)
		Facilitating and stimulating the unleashing of innovation potential through the first Pan EU-Africa sustainable network of Digital Innovation Hubs (DIHs) focussing on smart logistic. (DIGILOGIC)
		"Innovation Dialogues Europe-Africa" D4D Hub (IDEA D4D Hub)
		ECOSOLVE - Innovative solutions against environmental crime
		EU Policy and Outreach Partnerships
		Global Exchange on Religion in Society
		Cultural Relations Platform
		Social media 4 Peace
		Promoting the role of women in security and counterterrorism
		Open Internet Africa
		African Business Incubator Communities (BIC Africa)
		African Union Research Grants
		African Connect Initiative
		Tuning Africa 2015 – 2018
		IST-Africa
The Next Society		
UbuntuNet Alliance		
WACREN		

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

	ASREN
Education and Research	AU-EU Innovation Agenda = 87 sub-initiatives
	EU-Africa partnership in Space and Earth Observation
	Global Partnership for Education
	Investing in Young Businesses in Africa
	Regional Centres of Excellence
	Regional Teachers Initiative for Africa
	VET Toolbox 2: Enhanced Delivery of Demand-driven Skills Development for Investment in Africa
	Youth Mobility for Africa
Climate and Energy	Africa-Europe Green Energy
	Climate adaptation and resilience in Africa (Pillar III and IV) in Africa
	Climate Change Adaptation and Resilience in Africa
	NaturAfrica
Health	Digital Health for Health Systems Strengthening and Universal Health Coverage (UHC) in Sub-Saharan Africa
	Sexual and Reproductive Health and Rights (SRHR) in Sub-Saharan Africa
	Team Europe Initiative on manufacturing and access to vaccines, medicines and health technologies in Africa
	Team Europe Support Structure (TESS) for MAV in Africa
Transport	Global Maritime Technology Cooperation Centres (phase 2)
	Sustainable Aviation Fuels
Kenya	Digital
	Human-Centered Digitisation Initiative in Kenya
	Establish 10 Regional ICT & Innovation Centre of Excellence –
	Establish and operationalise the startup Fund for innovators
	Establishment of a testing and certification scheme for software, hardware, and ICT professionals
	Establishment of 1450 Village digital hubs for citizen digital literacy training, film production and public access to government services
	National Spatial Data Infrastructure to provide trusted geospatial data for businesses and government
	Regional Smart ICT Hub- to provide faster IP exchange and data storage for the Africa Region.
	Digital Content Cloud infrastructure for learning materials for all learners
	Digital Literacy Capacity Building for 20million citizens to be able to utilize technology in their businesses and access to government e-services
	Capacity Building for, 10,000 ICT professionals on high-end skills, 300,000 public servants and 350,000 teachers to given them necessary IT proficiency to be able to deliver services effectively to the citizen
	Digital Literacy Programme to accelerate integration of technology in teaching and learning in all learning institutions

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

	Annual International ICT Expo to show case on existing products and services for entrepreneurs and businesses	
	Harmonization/enactment of policies, legislations to enable ease of doing ICT businesses in the country.	
	Enactment of e-government legislation to support resource mobilization to fund the Masterplan Programmes	
Tanzania	Climate and Energy (C&E)	
	Olkaria I & IV Uprating project in Kenya	
	Transfer of innovative Polish biogas technology to the agricultural sector in Kenya	
	Zambia – Tanzania – Kenya (ZTK) Interconnector	
Digital	Investing in mobile networks in Madagascar and Tanzania	
Education	Gender Transformative Action in Tanzania - Education and Research	
Health	Construction of Kakono Hydropower Plant in Tanzania	
	Critical raw materials (CRM) Partnership Roadmap in Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia	
	Msimbazi Basin Development Project in Tanzania	
Ghana	C&E	
	Solar power plant Kaleo in Ghana	
Health	Health Manufacturing and access to vaccines, medicines and health technology products in Senegal, Rwanda, Ghana, and South Africa	
	MAV+ in Southern Africa: Rwanda, Senegal and Ghana	
Transport	Rehabilitation feeder and farm roads in Ghana	
Senegal	Digital	
	The Fonds d'Impulsion pour la Recherche Scientifique et Technique (FIRST) (Fund for Scientific and Technical Research)	
	The Grand Prix du Président de la République pour les Sciences et la Technologie (GPRST) (The President of the Republic's Grand Price for Science and Technology)	
	The Fonds de Publication scientifique et technique (FPST) (The Scientific and Technical Publication Fund)	
	The Fonds National de Recherches Agricoles et Agro-alimentaires (FNRAA) (National Fund for Agricultural and Agro-Food Research)	
	The Fonds de Promotion de l'Industrie Cinématographique et Audiovisuelle (FOPICA) (Fund for the Promotion of the Cinematographic and Audiovisual Industry)	
	Fonds de Financement Formation Professionnelle et Technique (3FPT) (Fund for Financing Professional and Technical Training)	
	Banque Nationale de Développement Economique (BNDE) (National Bank for Economic Development).	
	Délégation à l'Entreprenariat Rapide (DER) (Delegation for Rapid Entrepreneurship)	
	Climate and Energy	Irrigation programme PARIIS and rural development programme PADAER II in Senegal
		Just Energy Transition Partnership in Senegal
		Cleanup of Hann Bay (Dakar) in Senegal
	Health	Health Manufacturing and access to vaccines, medicines and health technology products in Senegal, Rwanda, Ghana, and South Africa
MAV+ in Southern Africa: Rwanda, Senegal and Ghana		
Transport	Casamance project: upgrade and operation of the port of Ziguinchor in Senegal	

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

<i>South Africa</i>		Construction of Bus Rapid Transit system in Dakar, Senegal	
		Development of Dakar Bus Public Transport Network in Senegal	
		Rehabilitation of the road Bissau/Safim - Mpack/Senegal border (115 km), Guinea Bissau	
	Digital	Implementation of Time Synchronization System in South Africa	
	Climate and Energy		Bio2Watt plants expansion in South Africa: producing biogas from animal waste and other waste sources
			Financial platforms for green hydrogen in South Africa and Namibia
		Just Energy Transition Partnership in South Africa	

More Initiatives here – [Dashboard of Initiatives](#)

4.1 Tools and Services

<i>Initiative/Link</i>	Tools and Services	Description
<i>Catalytic Africa - https://catalytic-africa.com/</i>	Catalytic Africa Platform for Match Funding opportunity	Connection of founders, angel investors, innovation hubs, VCs and policy makers, through dedicated webinars
<i>HUBiquitous - https://lab.waziup.io/</i>	Learning Center for IoT Capacity Building	End to end capacity building platform on IoT
<i>DIGILOGIC - https://digilogic.africa/elearning-platform/</i>	E-learning platform with on-demand training	Platform empowering innovators and professionals in entrepreneurship, digital skills and smart logistics
<i>African Union Higher Education Harmonization and Quality Assurance</i>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Networking - Exchanges - Dialogue and Training 	

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

5 CONCLUSION

The gaps and recommendations identified in this deliverable will be fundamental for the definition of activities in the later work packages. The tools and services as well will work as a good guide for the suitable services to enhance the Enrich in Africa platform. The next Deliverable 2.2 will provide an in-depth analysis of this result with the expected output of refined recommendations to ensure more success in the enhancement of the Europe – Africa Digital R&I cooperation.

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

6 ANNEXES

List of Key Policies Per Region

<i>Region</i>	<i>Policy</i>
<i>AU - EU</i>	Towards an African digital single market: Opportunities for the AU-EU partnership
	Insurance Industry Report for the Period
	Digital ECONOMY REPORT2021, Cross-border data flows and development:
	A Digital Single Market Strategy for Europe
	A new EU industrial deal with developing countries
	Made by Africa CREATING VALUE THROUGH INTEGRATION
	RULES OF ORIGIN Manual
	Strengthening the EU's partnership with Africa A new Africa-Europe Alliance for Sustainable Investment and Jobs
	AU Data Policy Framework
	Global Gateway: Where now and where to next?
	Policy Guidelines for Digitizing Teaching and Learning in Africa
	The Coordinated Programme of Economic and Social Development Policies
	Policy Guidelines on Digitizing Teaching and Learning in Africa
	Digital Financial Services Policy
	National Medium-Term Dev. Policy Framework
	National AfCFTA Policy Framework and Action Plan
	Single Window Make It Happen
	Building strategic European digital cooperation with Africa
	AU-EU Innovation Agenda
	Recommendations on how to make R&I a driver for sustainable development in AU-EU relations
	Horizon Europe Boots, Again, EU-Africa cooperation The Africa Initiative II
	The Global Gateway
	Horizon Europe - Africa Initiative 2021-2022
	Untangling the political economy of African regional organizations – Synthesis report
	AU Interoperability Framework for Digital ID
	African Union Convention on Cyber Security and Personal Data Protection
<i>Kenya</i>	National Information, Communications and Technology (ICT) Policy
	SCIENCE, TECHNOLOGY AND INNOVATION POLICY (draft)
	KENYA NATIONAL INNOVATION POLICY FRAMEWORK (proposed)
	Science, Technology and Innovation Policy Instruments for Sustainable Development goals,
	Guidelines for Cooperation and Management of Innovation Hubs in Kenya

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

	Science Technology and Innovation act
	Research and Innovation policy - Southeastern Kenya University
	The Kenya National System of Innovation
	Insurance Industry Report for the Period
	Private sector participation in agricultural policymaking in Kenya
<i>Ghana</i>	Ghana ICT for Accelerated Development (ICT4AD) Policy
	National Science, Technology and Innovation Policy
	Science, Technology & Innovation Policy Review
	Digitalisation of Basic Services in Ghana: State of Policies in Action and Lesson for Progress
	STI Ecosystem in Ghana
	Ghana National Data Sharing Policy Draft 3.0
	Ghana Innovation Ecosystem Insights, Challenges & Opportunities
	Ghana STI for SDG's policy roadmap
	National Medium-Term Dev. Policy Framework
	Prioritizing Ghana's Aflatoxin Policy Implementation Plan using P-IMA
	Empowering small-scale farmers (SPEARS)
	Ghana Industrial Policy
<i>Senegal</i>	Law relating to the creation and promotion of Startups in Senegal (Startup Act)
	Creation of "Agence Sénégalaise pour la Propriété Industrielle et l'Innovation technologique" (ASPIT) Agency for Industrial Property and Technological Innovation (ASPIT)
	Law on the protection of personal data in Senegal
	Diagnosis on the effectiveness of national fisheries and aquaculture policies and strategies for food and nutritional security in West Africa
<i>South Africa</i>	White Paper on Science, Technology and Innovation
	National Development Plan 2030 (NDP)
	Southern African Development Community (SADC) R&D Policy Framework:

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

List of Key Strategies Per Region

Region	Strategy
AU - EU	EU and Africa working together on Research and Innovation
	CGIAR 2030 Research and Innovation Strategy
	Science Technology and innovation ecosystem in Africa
	EU-Africa cooperation in Research & Innovation
	THE DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION STRATEGY FOR AFRICA (2020-2030)
	Strengthening the digital partnership between Africa and Europe
	Science, Technology, and Innovation Strategy for Africa 2024 (STISA-2024)
	Digital Transformation Strategy for Africa (2020-2030)
	Global Monitoring for Environment and Security and Africa Support Programme: Training Strategy
	National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy
	Europe's strategy for international cooperation in a changing world
	Towards a comprehensive strategy with Africa
	Europe's global approach to cooperation in research and innovation: strategic, open, and reciprocal
	A global approach to research and innovation
	Annual Report on the African Economy
	Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA)
	Digital Transformation Strategy - Seamless Citizen Experience through integrated government - Strategic Plan 2020 - 2025
	National Research and Development Strategy (NRDS)
	National Bioeconomy Strategy
	Kenya
THE KENYA NATIONAL DIGITAL MASTER PLAN	
Mapping Research and Innovation in the Republic of Kenya	
The Achilles' heel of Kenya's growing digital economy	
Kenya National Innovation Agency Strategic Plan 2023-2027	
National Research Priorities	
Institutional Science and Technology Strategy	
Kenya 10 year Innovation Master Plan	
CGIAR 2030 Research and Innovation Strategy	
Public Service Delivery innovation Strategy	
Research Innovation and Technology Sector	
SUMMARY FINDINGS FROM NATIONAL CONSULTATION IN KENYA	
Ghana	

WP 2 – D2.1 – Mapping of AU-EU digital ecosystems, initiatives, services and policy

	Ghana National Artificial Intelligence Strategy
	National Cybersecurity Policy Strategy
	Ghana STI4SDGs
	National Climate Change Adaptation Strategy
	Ghana National Export Development Strategy (NEDS) Overview 2020
	Ghana National Single Window Strategic Action Plan and Roadmap
	GHANA NATIONAL EXPORT STRATEGY
<i>Senegal</i>	Stratégie Sénégal Numérique 2025
	PSNRI
	Stratégie nationale des données
	Strategic Development Plan 2016-2020
<i>South Africa</i>	Five Year Strategic plan For 2020/21 – 2024/25
	South Africa's digital readiness for the fourth industrial revolution
	South Africa's National Research and Development Strategy (NRDS):
	National Research and Development Strategy (NRDS)
	National Bioeconomy Strategy

